

Connecting FAIR Digital Objects and Data Products for Engineering Sciences

Subtitle

Andreas Noback¹

¹TU Darmstadt, Darmstadt, Germany

²RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany

*Correspondence: Marius Politze, politze@itc.rwth-aachen.de

Abstract

Services of NFDI4ING to integrate the creation of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) into existing scientific workflows. An important aspect is the availability of FDOs within the service landscape, including their creation and programmatic access, while also making a connection with application from industry.

In general, an FDO is defined as a machine-readable and machine actionable unit of data that is identified by a PID and described by a record. The FDO record therefore should include the most critical information about the objects' context and possible operations. The context should be a minimal set of metadata, in the sense that it should allow discovery and re-usability. Operations define how to access the binary data and further metadata – they can be as simple as a HTTP GET (transfer a single file) or a description of a complex interface (e.g., for a Web Map Tile Service or a SPARQL endpoint). Ultimately, an FDO is a technical incarnation of the FAIR principles. Being widely technology and platform independent, the FDO concept eases long term interoperability, spanning across different system life-times or implementations [1], [2].

With the implementation of the FDO concept, it is further possible to separate data storage, PID registration, metadata and publication in building blocks, allowing a more modular architecture [3]. Several flavors of FDOs are evolving in the community, with great effort to ensure that these are compatible semantically. Within the data management platform Coscine we are aiming to translate and map several flavors [4]. Services like Coscine can further act as a hub or layer between different representations for decentralized systems landscapes and bridge to other (commercial) European data spaces, e.g. Catena-X via the Dataspace protocol¹. Coscine is complemented by a series of local NFDI4ING tools that help researchers to use semantic metadata profiles². These can be developed, typed and shared utilizing the NFDI4ING metadata profile service [5]. For research related to the built environment, the NFDI4ING ingest

¹<https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/dataspace-protocol>, accessed at 2024-04-24

²e.g. RDF store <https://gitlab.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/rokit/rdf-store>, accessed at 2024-04-24

Figure 1. FAIR Digital Objects and FAIR Data Products

service supports building information models based on the IFC standard as well as point-clouds³.

Within the context of more industrial applications comes the notion of a Data Product [6]. While a data products' definition originates from the FAIR principles, building a FAIR Data Product with an FDO at its base further assures inherent technical capabilities. On the other hand, Data Products bring in concepts of value, ownership, quality standards or life-cycle management related to the data itself (cf. Figure 1).

Author contributions

Andreas Noback — Investigation, Writing – original draft.

Marius Politze — Investigation, Writing – original draft.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

This work has been supported by NFDI4Ing (DFG – project number 442146713).

References

- [1] M. Politze et al., “Long term interoperability of distributed research data infrastructures,” *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure*, vol. 1, Sep. 2023. DOI: [10.52825/cordi.v1i.348](https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.348).
- [2] M. Politze, B. Heinrichs, S. Hunke, I. Lang, and T. Eifert, “Fair digital objects: Fairtilizer for the digital harvest,” in *EPiC Series in Computing*, vol. 105, EasyChair, 2025, pp. 284–274. DOI: [10.29007/hfzk](https://doi.org/10.29007/hfzk).
- [3] D. Schmitz and M. Politze, “Forschungsdaten managen – bausteine für eine dezentrale, forschungsnahe unterstützung,” *o-bib. Das offene Bibliotheksjournal*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 76–91, 2018. DOI: [10.5282/o-bib/2018H3S76-91](https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/2018H3S76-91).
- [4] B. Heinrichs, S. Hunke, and M. Politze, “Combining fair digital object implementation concepts in a real-life application,” *Open Conference Proceedings*, vol. 5, Mar. 2025, ISSN: 2749-5841. DOI: [10.52825/ocp.v5i.1173](https://doi.org/10.52825/ocp.v5i.1173).

³<https://ingest.nfdi4ing.de>, accessed at 2024-04-24

- [5] M. Grönewald et al., “Mit aims zu einem metadatenmanagement 4.0: Faire forschungsdaten benötigen interoperable metadaten,” de, *E-Science-Tage 2021: share your research data / herausgegeben von Vincent Heuveline und Nina Bisheh E-Science-Tage 2021*, vol. Heidelberg, 2022. DOI: [10.11588/HEIBOOKS.979.C13721](https://doi.org/10.11588/HEIBOOKS.979.C13721).
- [6] Z. Dehghani, *Data mesh*, en. Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly Media, Mar. 2022.